

EFFECT OF SUPERHEATED STEAM TREATMENT ON TENSILE STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBER AND FIBER-RESIN INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH

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1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has attracted much attention for various applications, such as aircraft materials, automotive parts, high pressure gas vessels and windmill blades, due to its light-weight, high-strength and -stiffness properties. However, the high production cost of carbon fiber has limited the widespread application of CFRP and the increasing quantity of CFRP waste in the future is also of concern. Therefore, the development of a high-efficiency and low-cost recycling process for CFRP waste is the most effective solution to these issues.

There have been various investigations on the recovery of carbon fibers from CFRP. Pyrolysis [1,2], the thermal decomposition of polymers in an inert gas, is the most common carbon fiber recovery process; however a resin residue is likely to remain after pyrolysis. Solvolysis using an organic solvent under ambient pressure [3] and decomposition using supercritical or subcritical fluid [4,5] has the advantage of both resin and carbon fiber recovery. However, there is a possibility of negative environmental impact and a scaling-up difficulty with the use of organic solvent and the requirement of a pressure vessel.

Superheated steam (SHS) has received much attention as a heat medium in recent years. SHS is dry steam at a temperature above the boiling point of water at atmospheric pressure. It has a high heat transfer coefficient, and thus enables rapid and

uniform heating. Drying rates with SHS are faster than that with conventional hot air above the inversion temperature (typically in the range of 423-473 K) [6]. SHS also provides a low P_{O_2} environment, so that it has been applied to various industrial applications such as drying, food processing and sterilization. In addition, SHS treatment has been reported to be effective for the rapid debinding of the green compact ceramics with organic binders [7].

Considering these features, the treatment of CFRP with SHS has the potential to quickly decompose the matrix resin and enable carbon fiber extraction without deterioration by oxidation. Furthermore, SHS treatment is expected to produce many surface hydroxyl groups on the carbon fiber, which act as active sites for the adhesion of resin. On the other hand, commercial carbon fibers are typically coated with a sizing agent to improve the adhesion between carbon fiber and resin. If SHS treatment enables the simultaneous recovery of carbon fiber from CFRP and surface modification of the recovered fiber without deterioration of the fiber strength, then lowering of the CFRP production costs could be expected by the use of sizing-free recycled carbon fibers.

The purpose of this study is to clarify the effect of SHS treatment on the tensile strength of carbon monofilament, the shear strength of the fiber-epoxy resin interface in CFRP and chemical states of fiber surface.

2 Experimental

2.1 Specimen

TORAYCA@T700 carbon fiber (Toray Industries Inc., Tokyo, Japan) without a sizing agent (unsized fiber) was used as the test specimen.

2.2 SHS Treatment

SHS was produced using an induction-heating (IH) system. An IH-type SHS generator has the advantage of precise temperature control and rapid heating, although the constituent materials must have excellent corrosion resistance to high temperature steam and thermal shock resistance. To generate clean SHS at the temperature above 773 K using IH system, electrically conductive $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{MnO}_{3+\delta}$ and Al_2TiO_5 ceramics were selected as the heater and chamber materials, respectively [7,8].

An unsized fiber bundle was exposed to SHS at a flow rate of 5 kg/h. The specimen was placed in the process chamber at 673 K and held for 5 min at 773–1073 K. Removal of the specimen was conducted at 673 K. Both the heating and cooling rate was 20 K/min.

The stability of the carbon materials was estimated using FactSage thermodynamic equilibrium calculation software (Thermfact/CRCT, Montreal, Canada and GTT Technologies, Aachen, Germany) [9,10]. Figure 1 shows the equilibrium oxygen partial pressures (P_{O_2}) for H_2O with dissolved oxygen (D.O.) at 7350 or 0 $\mu\text{g/L}$ and the thermodynamic phase equilibrium line for the C–CO, CO_2 system. Carbon is stable in the region below the equilibrium line of the C–CO, CO_2 system, so that carbon materials are considered to oxidize in SHS with any concentrations of D.O. Thus, when CFRP waste is treated with SHS, it is necessary to kinetically suppress oxidization of the carbon fiber. The D.O. concentration of the water, which is not controlled by any treatment such as an inert gas bubbling, was measured to be 7350 $\mu\text{g/L}$. The open circles in Fig. 1 indicate the estimated P_{O_2} values for the SHS treatment conditions used in the present study.

Fig. 1 Equilibrium oxygen partial pressures for (a) H_2O (D.O.=7350 $\mu\text{g/L}$), (b) H_2O (D.O.=0 $\mu\text{g/L}$) and (c) the phase thermodynamic equilibrium line for the C–CO, CO_2 system. Open circles indicate the estimated oxygen partial pressures for the SHS treatment conditions used in this study.

2.3 Evaluation

Carbon fiber coated with a sizing agent (sized fiber) was also evaluated as a control specimen in addition to the unsized fiber treated with SHS.

The diameter and surface morphology of the carbon fibers were examined using field emission-scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM; S-4500 and SU-8000, Hitachi High-Technologies Corp., Tokyo, Japan). Twenty filaments were observed for each carbon fiber specimen to determine the fiber diameters.

Tensile strength testing of carbon monofilaments was performed using a universal testing machine (5582, Instron Corp, Norwood, USA) with a 10 N load cell. Tensile strength specimens were prepared by fixing a monofilament onto a paper holder with adhesive. The specimen was set up to the testing machine and the paper holder was then cut into two parts before testing. The gauge length was 20 mm and a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min was used. All tests were conducted at room temperature. Twenty specimens were tested for fiber treated with SHS

**EFFECT OF SUPERHEATED STEAM TREATMENT ON TENSILE STRENGTH
OF CARBON FIBER AND FIBER-RESIN INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH**

and fifty specimens were tested for the untreated sized and unsized fibers. The tensile strength σ_f , was determined using:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{4P}{\pi d_f^2} \quad (1)$$

where P is the maximum load and d_f is the fiber diameter.

The interfacial shear strength between the carbon fiber and resin was determined by single fiber fragmentation tests. Flat bone-shaped single fiber composite specimens (50 mm long and 2 mm thick) were prepared using a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) mold. Bisphenol-A type epoxy resin (#828, Mitsubishi Chemical Corp., Tokyo, Japan) was used as a matrix resin with triethylenetetramine (Mitsubishi Chemical Corp., Tokyo, Japan) as a curing agent. A mixture of the matrix resin and curing agent was cast into the mold containing a single fiber running along the center. The specimen was kept at room temperature for 24 h and then heated from room temperature to 323 K and held for 60 min. The specimen temperature was increased again from 323 to 373 K and held for 80 min. Finally, the temperature was slowly reduced from 373 K to room temperature. The composites specimen obtained were carefully polished with diamond slurry so that the fragment length of embedded carbon monofilament could be precisely observed using a microscope. Then, the specimen was strained in steps until no further fragmentation of carbon fiber occurred. The interfacial shear strength τ_i , was calculated using equations (2) and (3) [11,12]:

$$\tau_i = K \frac{d_f \sigma_f(\bar{l})}{2\bar{l}} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_f(\bar{l}) = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{\bar{l}}{l_0} \right) \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{m} \right) \quad (3)$$

where K is a constant, $\sigma_f(\bar{l})$ is the strength of a fiber fragment at the saturation length \bar{l} , l_0 is the gauge

length for the tensile strength test, σ_0 and m are the scale and shape parameters of the Weibull distributions for the tensile strength, respectively, and Γ is the gamma function. Three specimens were tested for each carbon fiber type.

The surface chemical states of the carbon fibers were analyzed using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS; ESCA 3057, Ulvac-Phi Inc., Chigasaki, Japan) with Al K α as an X-ray source (1486.6 eV). The XPS takeoff angle was set at 45°, which enabled the system to detect photoelectrons to a depth of 5 to 10 nm from the surface.

The titration method proposed by Boehm [13,14] was used to determine the concentration of acidic and basic surface functional groups on the carbon fibers. The unsized virgin (untreated) fiber and fiber treated with SHS at 993 K were evaluated in this study. The acidic surface properties are caused by the presence of carboxylic, lactonic and hydroxyl groups of phenolic character. These groups differ in their acidities and can be differentiated by neutralization with aqueous solutions of NaHCO₃, Na₂CO₃ and NaOH, respectively. NaHCO₃ neutralizes only carboxylic groups, while Na₂CO₃ neutralizes both carboxylic and lactonic groups, and NaOH neutralizes carboxylic, lactonic and hydroxyl groups. The specimens were mixed with aqueous solutions of 0.05 N NaHCO₃, Na₂CO₃ or NaOH, respectively. The excess base in the supernatant solutions was then titrated against 0.05 N HCl. Carboxylic groups were quantified by direct titration with NaHCO₃. The difference between titration with Na₂CO₃ and that with NaHCO₃ was assumed to be lactone, and the difference between the titration with NaOH and that with Na₂CO₃ was assumed to be phenol groups. Similarly, the concentration of basic sites on the fiber surface was determined by mixing the specimen with 0.05 N HCl and back-titration of the obtained supernatant solutions with 0.05 N NaOH.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Diameter and surface morphology

Figure 2 shows the carbon fiber diameter as a function of the SHS treatment temperatures. The diameters of the unsized and sized virgin fibers are also shown for reference. The diameters of all the treated fibers were almost the same as those of the virgin sized and unsized fibers that did not undergo SHS treatment.

SEM observation of the carbon fibers was performed at a low acceleration voltage of 1 kV to examine the surface morphology. Fig. 3 shows representative SEM micrographs of the unsized virgin fiber and the fiber after SHS treatment at 1073 K. The surface smoothness of the fiber treated at 1073 K is similar to that of the non-treated fiber, as shown in the higher magnification SEM images (Fig. 3s (b) and (d)). SEM observation revealed no obvious morphological change of the carbon fiber surface after SHS treatment.

Fig. 2 Carbon fiber diameter as a function of SHS treatment temperature. The error bars indicate standard deviations in the measured values.

Fig. 3 SEM images of the (a, b) unsized virgin fiber and (c, d) fiber after SHS treatment at 1073 K.

EFFECT OF SUPERHEATED STEAM TREATMENT ON TENSILE STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBER AND FIBER-RESIN INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH

3.2 Tensile strength

Figure 4 shows the tensile strength of carbon monofilament as a function of the SHS treatment temperature. The scale σ_0 , and shape m , parameters from the Weibull distributions for the tensile strength of each carbon fiber are listed in Table 1. The strength of the fiber after SHS treatment at 773 K maintained the initial level, whereas it was reduced to lower than that of the unsized virgin fiber after treatment above 873 K and generally decreased with increasing SHS treatment temperature. The carbon fiber is oxidized by SHS treatment, as indicated in Fig. 1; therefore, the degree of oxidation of the carbon fiber by SHS may increase for treatment temperature above 873 K, resulting in a decrease in the tensile strength of the fibers.

Fig. 4 Tensile strength of carbon fibers as a function of the SHS treatment temperature. The error bars represent standard deviations in the measured values.

Table 1 Scale parameters (σ_0) and shape parameters (m) of the Weibull distributions for the tensile strength of carbon fibers treated with SHS.

Fibers	Treatment conditions		Scale parameter, σ_0 (GPa)	Shape parameter, m
	Atmospheres	Temperatures (K)		
Sized	Non-treatment		4.19	5.77
Unsized	Non-treatment		4.02	5.33
	SHS	773	4.20	4.92
		873	3.82	4.40
		973	3.61	4.00
1073		3.39	4.72	

3.3 Interfacial shear strength between carbon fiber and epoxy resin

The adhesion between the carbon fiber and epoxy matrix resin was measured using the single fiber fragmentation test on fibers that had been treated with SHS and the results are plotted in Fig. 5 as the interfacial shear strength of fiber-resin against the SHS treatment temperature. The interfacial shear strength between the treated fiber and resin increased with the SHS treatment temperature up to 873 K, above which it became constant. The interfacial shear strength of fiber-resin after SHS treatment above 873 K was approximately twice that of the unsized virgin fiber and was within the error range of that for the sized fiber.

Fig. 5 Interfacial shear strength between the treated carbon fiber and epoxy resin as a function of the SHS treatment temperature. The error bars correspond to standard deviations in the measured values.

3.4 Surface chemical states

Figure 6 shows XPS spectra of the C 1s region for unsized virgin fiber and fiber after SHS treatment at 973 K. No appreciable difference of the spectra was identified after SHS treatment. This result is thought

to be caused by the radiation damage during the XPS measurement.

Table 2 summarizes the concentration of acidic and basic properties on the surface of the carbon fibers as determined by Boehm titration. The total amount of basic functionalities on the carbon fiber surface was not changed after SHS treatment. However, the amount of hydroxyl groups of phenolic character on the fiber surface increased after SHS treatment. Thus, it was clarified that the SHS treatment is effective for the increase of surface hydroxyl groups on carbon fiber. Although the concentration of other acidic surface groups on the fiber surface was not changed after SHS treatment, the treated fiber has 1.8 times as large as the amount of total acidity compared with the non-treated fiber. The hydroxyl groups induced on the fiber surface are considered to act as active sites for the adhesion of resin, and therefore the interfacial shear strength between fiber and resin is improved.

Fig. 6 XPS spectra for the C1s region of (a) unsized virgin fiber and (b) fiber treated with SHS at 973 K, together with the peak assignment of surface functional groups on carbon fiber [15].

EFFECT OF SUPERHEATED STEAM TREATMENT ON TENSILE STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBER AND FIBER-RESIN INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH

Table 2 Surface acidic and basic properties of unsized fiber with and without SHS treatment determined by Boehm titration.

Fibers	Treatment conditions		Total basicity (meq/g)	Acidity (meq/g)			
	Atmosphere	Temperature (K)		Total	Carboxylic groups	Lactonic groups	Phenolic groups
Unsize	Non-treatment		0.097	0.073	0	0.073	0
	SHS	973	0.097	0.131	0.001	0.073	0.058

4 Conclusions

The effect of SHS treatment on the morphological, mechanical and chemical properties of carbon fiber was investigated. Carbon fiber was treated with SHS in the temperature range of 773 to 1073 K.

The diameter of the treated fiber was the same as that of virgin fiber. No difference in the surface morphology of the fiber before and after SHS treatment was identified by SEM observation. The tensile strength of the fiber after SHS treatment was decreased at temperature above 893 K and generally decreased with increasing SHS treatment temperature. Adhesion at the interface between the treated fiber and epoxy resin was improved by SHS treatment at temperatures up to 893 K, above which the interfacial shear strength became constant. Fibers after SHS treatment above 873 K had approximately twice the interfacial shear strength of unsized virgin fiber. In addition, Boehm titration results indicated that SHS treatment increases the concentration of hydroxyl groups on carbon fiber, which effectively promotes the interfacial adhesion between carbon fiber and epoxy resin.

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